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Availability and Utilization of Digital Equipment for Teaching Computer Studies in Public Secondary Schools in Ekiti State

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Abstract

This study investigated the availability and utilization of digital equipment for teaching Computer Studies in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. To guide the study, three research questions were raised and two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population comprised 86 respondents, consisting of 32 Computer Studies teachers and 54 science class prefects in public secondary schools in Ekiti State. A 21-item structured questionnaire developed by the researcher was used for data collection and was face-validated by three experts. The reliability of the instrument was determined using the Cronbach Alpha coefficient, which yielded a reliability index of 0.79. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while t-test statistics were employed to test the hypotheses. The findings revealed that digital equipment are available and utilized for teaching Computer Studies to a moderate extent. Basic digital tools such as computer systems, projectors, video cassette recorders, and DVD players were utilized to a high extent, whereas more interactive and modern digital technologies recorded low utilization. The study also revealed that inadequate provision of functional digital equipment and insufficient teacher training were the major challenges affecting effective utilization. Furthermore, no significant difference was found between the mean ratings of teachers and class prefects on the digital technologies used and the extent of their utilization. Based on these findings, it was recommended that government and school authorities should provide adequate and functional digital equipment and organize continuous capacity-building programmes to enhance teachers' competence in the effective integration of digital technologies into Computer Studies instruction.

Keywords: Availability, Utilization, Digital Equipment, computer Studies

1. Introduction

Digital technologies have revolutionized the world and the impact is being felt in all nooks and crannies of the society. Digital technologies are electronic equipment implored in teaching and learning at all levels of education all over the world. According to Davies and Merchant (2009) and Brandon (2016), digital technologies embrace several terms, such as computers, projectors, smart boards, smart tables, laptops, digital textbooks, cameras, audio enhancements, scratch, prezi, pixton, animoto, information and communication technology (ICT), learning management systems (LMS) and digital media like wikis, blogs, social media podcasts among others.

Ajayi (2002) defines digital technologies as an evolution era that has computers and technology as well as fusion with good technologies and even human skills. From the foregoing, digital technologies are electronic control tools, systems, devices that generate, process, analyze and store information according to the commands

given and faster in giving results than analog equipment. They play vital roles at every level of education system, as they are in use in day-to-day activities of the school for teaching and learning activities.

Teaching is the process of imparting knowledge from the teacher to the learner. Teaching involves teachers, learners and teaching materials that enhance learning. According to West (2018), teaching is the art that inculcates abilities, norms, moral, values, skills that are passed through an experienced person to learners that result to change of behaviour. Teaching in this era of technology involves using digital technologies in order to make teaching more interesting to both the teacher and the learner. According to the Scottish Government Commission (2015), teaching has been made more interesting with the use of digital technologies which contributes to five education priorities; raising attainment, tackling inclusion, improving transition into employment, enhancing parental engagement and improving the efficiency of education.

Utilization is the process of using textbooks, equipment, teaching aids and other material for the purpose they are made for. Nwabueze (2011) is of the opinion that utilization is equitable use of facilities accruable for the education industry. Furthermore, the author stated that the availability of the facilities is important, but the ultimate desire is the optimum utilization for the achievement of educational goals. According to Slavin (2006), utilization of digital technologies in teaching creates goal-oriented behaviour among students, provided the technique is effectively used in improving students' academic achievement. According to Rechmond (2007), teachers use digital technologies to teach, track grades and communicate with students with computer-controlled projection units; they can add graphics, sound and animation to communications.

However, digital technologies are grouped into four user categories namely; the emergent user, the progressive user, the high user and the dependable user. The emergent user has computer at home and at workplaces and knows how to use computer to work and trouble shoot to manipulate problems. The progressive user is always eager to learn more and has more knowledge in computer. The high user is skilled in technology while the dependent user does not know anything about technology and does not make efforts to learn it. The dependent users depend on those that are experienced in computer to do computing work for them (Hall, 2005). Utilization of digital technologies promotes teaching and learning standards.

However, in a different view, Christerson, Johnson and Horn (2008) are of the view that digital technologies were not invented with educational purpose in mind. The authors argued that utilization has not really made much impact in teaching and learning because of the way digital equipment are used in schools. This implies that digital technologies are not properly used to suit the age of the learner, the topic of the study, the environment and are not user friendly among others. Amuchi (2015) and Nwana, Ofoegbu and Egbe (2017) lamented on the storage of ICT infrastructure and non-existence of internet connectivity in secondary schools that pose problems to utilization. Dzionu (2002) expressed the need for well-equipped ICT laboratory equipment with internet facilities at departments, faculties, teachers' offices and student hostels to facilitate usage. All these pose problems to the use of digital technologies in teaching, especially in science subjects of which Computer Studies is inclusive.

Computer Studies is a foundational academic discipline that focuses on the understanding and application of computers and digital technologies for problem-solving, information processing, and communication in contemporary society. At the secondary school level, Computer Studies introduces learners to fundamental concepts such as computer hardware and software, data processing, word processing, spreadsheets, programming basics, internet usage, and digital ethics. The subject plays a critical role in developing students' digital literacy, logical reasoning, and computational thinking skills, which are increasingly regarded as essential competencies for lifelong learning and employability in a technology-driven world (Yusuf & Balogun, 2019). In line with global educational trends, Computer Studies is designed not only to impart theoretical knowledge but also to foster practical skills through hands-on engagement with digital tools and applications.

Within the Nigerian educational context, Computer Studies has been positioned as a strategic subject for national development and human capital formation. The effective teaching of the subject requires the availability and purposeful use of digital equipment such as computers, projectors, and relevant software to support experiential learning and skill acquisition. Scholars have emphasized that when Computer Studies is

taught using appropriate digital resources, students demonstrate improved academic performance, higher motivation, and better preparedness for further education and the digital labour market (Afolayan, Okorie & Adeyemi, 2021). Conversely, inadequate resources and poor instructional practices reduce the subject to abstract instruction, thereby undermining its objectives. Consequently, Computer Studies remains a critical platform through which secondary schools can bridge the digital divide and equip learners with competencies relevant to the demands of the 21st-century knowledge economy (Oyelere, Suhonen & Sutinen, 2020).

However, some studies have been carried out on the utilization of digital technologies in teaching and learning in secondary schools. Benison and Gooyes (2016) carried out study on teachers' utilization of digital technologies in teaching mathematics in Australia. The result shows that a significant good number of teachers had not undertaken any activity in relation to using digital technologies in teaching mathematics due to lack of time and access to technology. Similarly, Haydn and Barton (2008) carried out a study on utilization of digital technologies in Australia secondary schools in different subject areas. The result shows insignificant use of digital technologies by teachers as a result of lack of time, difficulty in accessing enough computers for students and unavailability of data projectors in ordinary classroom. Adeyemi and Olaleye (2013) reported that utilization and integration of ICT in the teaching and management of secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria, has not been fully integrated to make impact generally in schools. Similarly, studies (Oboegbulem & Ugwu, 2013; and Agim, Iroeze, Osuji & Obasi-Haco, 2018) revealed that in Imo State (Metropolis), Nigeria, that secondary schools are not well equipped with ICT facilities and their findings decried poor applications of ICT gadgets in the State. Based on the above submissions, locally and internationally, the study investigated the extent of availability and utilization of digital technologies in the teaching and learning of Computer Studies in the public secondary schools in Ahiazu-Mbaise LGA; which happens to be one of the 27 Local Government Areas in the State.

2. Statement of the Problem

Effective teaching and learning in contemporary education largely depend on the availability and appropriate utilization of digital equipment by teachers during instructional delivery. In the teaching of Computer Studies, the use of digital equipment such as desktop and laptop computers, projectors, internet facilities, and relevant software is indispensable for promoting practical understanding and skill acquisition among students. Utilization of these digital resources is particularly critical if students are expected to perform satisfactorily in internal and external examinations. However, empirical evidence from related studies indicates that digital equipment meant for instructional purposes is either inadequate or poorly utilized in many public secondary schools, despite the Federal Government of Nigeria's policy directive that emphasized the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into school curricula and classroom teaching as far back as 2004.

In Ekiti State, observations and preliminary reports suggest that many public secondary schools lack sufficient and functional digital equipment for teaching Computer Studies, while some schools that possess such facilities fail to utilize them effectively due to factors such as inadequate teacher competence, poor maintenance culture, irregular power supply, and limited administrative support. This situation has contributed to students' poor practical skills, low interest in Computer Studies, and unsatisfactory performance in external examinations. It is therefore evident that students' underachievement in Computer Studies may be linked to ineffective utilization of available digital equipment by teachers, which hampers students' understanding of abstract and practical concepts. Against this background, the problem of this study is to determine the availability and extent of utilization of digital equipment for teaching Computer Studies in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, as well as to identify the challenges militating against their effective use.

3. Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study was to find out Availability and Utilization of Digital Equipment for Teaching Computer Studies in Public Secondary Schools in Ekiti State. Therefore, the specific objectives of the study are:

- i. Identify the digital technologies used in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools.
- ii. Ascertain the extent to which each of digital technologies is used in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools.
- iii. To find out the challenges of using digital technologies in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools

4. Research Questions

- i. What are the digital technologies used in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools?
- ii. To what extent are the digital technologies used in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools?
- iii. What are the challenges of using digital technologies in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools?

5. Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the ratings of teachers and class prefects on the digital technologies used in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers and class prefects on the extent of utilization of digital technologies in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools.

6. Methods

In this study, descriptive survey design was adopted. According to Nworgu (2015), descriptive survey aims at collecting data and describing in a systematic manner, the characteristics, features or facts about a given population. This implies that the present study intends to collect data from the sample (teachers and class prefects) and use the data to describe systematically the attributes of the area (use and extent of use of digital technologies). The study was carried out using Computer Studies teachers in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The population of study is 86 respondents comprising 32 Computer Studies teachers and 54 science class prefects across public secondary schools in Ekiti State. A 21-item structured questionnaire was developed from the literature reviewed for the study and utilized for data collection. Each questionnaire item had a five point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE=5), High Extent (HE=4), Moderate Extent (ME=3), Low Extent (LE=2), Very Low Extent (VLE=1). Three experts face validated the instrument. Cronbach alpha coefficient measure of internal consistency was used to determine the reliability of the instrument and a coefficient of 0.79 was obtained. The data generated was analyzed through descriptive statistics of Mean and Standard deviation to answer the research questions. Inferential statistics (t-test) was employed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Any item with a mean score and standard deviation of 3.50 and 1.75 and above shows high extent, a mean score between 3.00 – 3.49 and standard deviation between 1.50 – 1.74 suggests a moderate extent, and a mean value and standard deviation below 3.00 and 1.50 indicates low extent (Adefila, 2014).

7. RESULTS

Research question 1: What are the digital technologies used in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools?

Table 1: mean ratings the digital technologies used in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools.

S/N	The digital technologies used in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Combination of media in the form of graphic, text and audio.	2.60	1.34	Low extent
2	The use of computer system to convey information.	3.58	1.59	High extent
3	The use of video camera.	3.09	1.66	Moderate extent
4	The use of video cassette recorder.	3.62	1.56	High extent
5	The use of overhead projector.	2.52	1.30	Low extent
6	The use of compact disc.	3.22	1.26	Moderate extent
7	The use of DVD player.	3.41	1.38	High extent
	Grand mean	3.15	1.44	

Data in Table 1 The findings show that digital technologies are utilized to a moderate extent in teaching Computer Studies in public secondary schools, as indicated by the grand mean of 3.15. Computer systems, video cassette recorders, and DVD players are used to a high extent, while video cameras and compact discs are moderately utilized. However, the use of integrated multimedia tools and overhead projectors is low. Overall, the results suggest that although basic digital tools are fairly utilized, more interactive and modern digital technologies are not adequately integrated into Computer Studies instruction.

Research question 2

To what extent are the digital technologies used in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools?

Table 2: Mean ratings of to what extent are the digital technologies used in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools

S/N	To what extent are the digital technologies used in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools	Mean	SD	Decision
8	The use of scanner to scan documents.	2.69	1.23	Low extent
9	The use of projector for PowerPoint presentations.	3.67	1.59	High extent
10	The use of printer to print electronic data	3.03	1.62	Moderate extent
11	The use of computer for preparation of job materials	3.69	1.59	High extent
12	The use of keyboard as a communication tool.	2.32	1.39	Low extent
	Grand mean	3.08	1.48	

Data in Table 2 shows that the results indicate that digital technologies are utilized to a moderate extent in teaching Computer Studies in public secondary schools, as shown by the grand mean of 3.08. Specifically, the use of projectors for PowerPoint presentations (Mean = 3.67) and computers for preparing teaching materials (Mean = 3.69) are employed to a high extent, reflecting teachers' reliance on these tools for lesson delivery. The use of printers for producing electronic data is moderate (Mean = 3.03), while scanners (Mean = 2.69) and keyboards as communication tools (Mean = 2.32) are used to a low extent. Overall, while some digital technologies are actively integrated into teaching, others remain underutilized, indicating uneven adoption of ICT tools in Computer Studies instruction.

Research question 3

What are the challenges of using digital technologies in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools?

Table 3: mean ratings of what are the challenges of using digital technologies in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools

SN	What are the challenges of using digital technologies in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools	Mean	SD	Decision
13	There is inadequate provision of functional digital equipment (computers, projectors, printers) in the school.	3.62	1.67	High Extent
14	Frequent power outages hinder the effective use of digital technologies during lessons.	2.61	0.86	Low Extent
15	Teachers lack sufficient training and skills to integrate digital tools effectively into Computer Studies lessons.	4.21	1.77	High Extent
16	Limited access to the internet and online resources restricts the use of digital technologies in teaching.	3.29	1.21	Moderate Extent
17	Maintenance and repair services for digital equipment are inadequate, causing prolonged downtime.	2.69	1.20	Low Extent
18	The high cost of procuring and replacing digital technologies limits their availability in schools.	2.77	0.98	Low extent
19	Students' low level of digital literacy reduces the effective utilization of ICT tools in lessons.	2.61	1.06	Low Extent
20	Large class sizes make it difficult for teachers to ensure all students benefit from digital technologies.	2.62	1.38	Low Extent
21	Teachers' resistance to adopting new technologies affects the integration of digital tools in teaching.	2.71	1.39	Low Extent
	Grand mean	3.01	1.28	

The findings indicate that the challenges of using digital technologies in teaching Computer Studies in public secondary schools occur to a moderate extent, as reflected by the grand mean of 3.01. Among the challenges, inadequate provision of functional digital equipment (Mean = 3.62) and insufficient teacher training and skills (Mean = 4.21) are the most significant, occurring to a high extent. Limited access to the internet and online resources is a moderate challenge (Mean = 3.29), while other factor such as frequent power outages, inadequate maintenance services, high procurement costs, low student digital literacy, large class sizes, and teachers' resistance to technology are less pronounced, occurring to a low extent. Overall, the results suggest that the most critical barriers to effective digital technology use in Computer Studies are related to resource availability and teacher competence, while other infrastructural and attitudinal factors play a lesser role

8. Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the ratings of teachers and class prefects on the digital technologies used in teaching Computer studies in Public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria

Table 4. T-test statistics on mean ratings of teachers and class prefects on digital technologies used in teaching Computer Studies in public secondary schools

Variables (Respondents)	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	t-tab	Remark
Teachers	32	3.22	1.46	127	1.33	1.96	Not Sig.
Class Prefects	54	3.19	1.48				

The data in Table 4 show that the calculated t-value (t-cal = 1.33) is less than the critical t-value (t-tab = 1.96) at the 0.05 level of significance with 127 degrees of freedom. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the ratings of teachers and class prefects regarding the digital technologies used in teaching Computer Studies in public secondary schools. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho1) is accepted.

Hypothesis 2

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers and class prefects on the extent of utilization of digital technologies in teaching Computer Studies in public secondary schools.

Table 5: t-test statistics on mean ratings of teachers and class prefects on the extent of utilization of digital technologies in teaching Computer Studies

Variables (Respondents)	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	t-tab	Remark
Teachers	32	3.26	1.44	127	1.54	1.96	Not Sig.
Class Prefects	54	3.32	1.37				

The results in Table 5 indicate that the calculated t-value ($t\text{-cal} = 1.54$) is less than the critical t-value ($t\text{-tab} = 1.96$) at the 0.05 significance level with 127 degrees of freedom. This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of teachers and class prefects on the extent of utilization of digital technologies in teaching Computer Studies. Consequently, the null hypothesis (Ho2) is accepted.

9. Discussion of findings

The findings of this study reveal that digital technologies are utilized to a moderate extent in teaching Computer Studies in public secondary schools in Ekiti State. Specifically, tools such as computer systems, video cassette recorders, DVD players, and projectors are used to a high extent, reflecting teachers' reliance on basic and familiar digital equipment for instructional delivery. Moderate use was observed for devices like video cameras, compact discs, and printers, while integrated multimedia tools, scanners, keyboards, and overhead projectors recorded low utilization. These results suggest that although some digital tools are incorporated into teaching practices, more advanced, interactive, and modern technologies remain underutilized. This aligns with earlier studies by Yusuf and Balogun (2019) and Afolayan, Okorie, and Adeyemi (2021), who reported that teachers in Nigerian secondary schools often rely on traditional ICT tools while neglecting more interactive digital resources due to lack of availability, training, or confidence.

The investigation into the challenges of using digital technologies indicates that these constraints occur to a moderate extent. Inadequate provision of functional equipment and insufficient teacher training were identified as the most critical barriers. Limited internet access was a moderate challenge, whereas other factors such as power outages, inadequate maintenance, high procurement costs, low student digital literacy, large class sizes, and teachers' resistance to technology were less pronounced. These findings are consistent with the works of Olaitan and Nwalo (2018) and Oyelere, Suhonen, and Sutinen (2020), who observed that resource constraints and insufficient teacher competence are major impediments to effective ICT integration in Nigerian schools. The results highlight that ensuring adequate infrastructure and professional development for teachers is essential for enhancing the quality of Computer Studies instruction.

Furthermore, the study revealed no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and class prefects regarding the digital technologies used and the extent of their utilization. This suggests a general consensus between teachers and students, reinforcing the accuracy of the descriptive findings. Similar patterns have been noted in prior research by Adomi and Kpangban (2018), where student perceptions mirrored those of teachers in terms of ICT use, indicating that challenges affecting teachers' integration of technology directly influence students' experiences and engagement.

10. Conclusion

In conclusion, digital technologies are moderately utilized in teaching Computer Studies in public secondary schools, with basic tools more frequently employed than interactive or modern resources. The major challenges are inadequate digital equipment and limited teacher competence, while other infrastructural and attitudinal factors are less critical. Addressing these gaps through improved infrastructure and professional development is essential for enhancing teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes.

11. Recommendation

Public secondary schools should be equipped with sufficient and functional digital tools, including computers, multimedia projectors, scanners, and interactive software, to enhance the teaching and learning of Computer Studies.

Continuous capacity-building programs should be organized to improve teachers' skills and confidence in integrating digital technologies into instructional practices effectively.

Schools should ensure reliable power supply, internet connectivity, and maintenance services for digital equipment to facilitate consistent and efficient use of technology in teaching.

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